

PHOTOSENSITISATION BY SOLIDS. PART II*. PHOTOSENSITISED OXIDATION OF AMMONIA IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION WITH TITANIA AS THE PHOTSENSITISER.

BY G. GOPALARAO AND K. S. MURTY.

The photosensitised oxidation of ammonia in aqueous solution has been studied in the visible light with titania as the photosensitiser. The reaction was found to be zero-molecular. From a study of the influence of concentration of ammonia on the reaction rate and of electrolytes it has been concluded that the reaction is a heterogeneous one occurring at the surface of titania, activated by the absorption of light. The reaction has also been studied in monochromatic light of different wave-lengths. The mechanism of photosensitisation is discussed. The results obtained and the conclusions arrived at lend considerable support to the mechanism proposed by Gopalarao in the previous part of this series of papers. Experimental results have also been given for the absorption of ammonia by ignited titania.

Photosensitisation by solids is of great practical and theoretical significance. Paints containing titanium dioxide show fading and this phenomenon has been discussed by Kiedel (*Farben Ztg.*, 1929, **34**, 1242), Wagner (*ibid.*, 1929, **34**, 1243; 1929, **36**, 257) and others. The manufacture of panchromatic photographic plates using various dyes as photosensitiser is at present an industry of considerable importance. The process of photosynthesis in the green plants involves photosensitisation by a solid, namely the green pigment chlorophyll. Our knowledge of the mechanism of this photosynthetic reaction is still obscure. The significance to soil chemistry of the results obtained on the photosensitised oxidation of ammonia and the oxidative deamination of amino-acids in light has been emphasised by Gopalarao and Dhar (*Soil Sci.*, 1931, **31**, 379), Gopalarao (*ibid.*, 1934, **38**, 143), Gopalarao and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 617) and Gopalarao and Pandalai (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 623).

In spite of the great importance of photosensitisation by solids very little attention has been paid to the mechanism of the phenomenon. Recently Gopalarao (Doctorate Thesis, University of Allahabad, 1934; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1939, **184A**, 377) discussed the mechanism of photosensitisation by titania, studying a typical reaction *viz.*, the oxidation of

* Part I of this series appeared in *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1939, **184A**, 377.

ammonia in ultraviolet light. In the present paper we are giving results of a detailed study of the same reaction in visible light.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The source of visible light was either a 500-watt or a 1000-watt Phillips' tungsten filament lamp. The lamp was connected in series with a thermostat and an ammeter. The 500-watt lamp was worked at 2.2 amperes and the 1000-watt one at 4.4 amperes, on a D.C. circuit. Each lamp was enclosed in a wooden box, painted dull black inside, with a circular aperture in the front. The light issuing out of the aperture was brought to focus by means of a glass condenser. The ammonia solution with the titania was kept in a stoppered quartz cylindrical vessel mounted in a thermostat with quartz windows. The temperature of the thermostat was maintained at $33^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ by constantly circulating water from another thermostat. The ammonia solution was taken out whenever required and the nitrite content estimated colorimetrically by the Greiss-Ilosvay method.

Influence of Concentration of Ammonia.

TABLE I.

40 ml. of $M/5$ -ammonia + 0.2 g. of ignited titania exposed for 10 hours to light from a 500-watt lamp.

Conc. of ammonia.	Nitrite-N formed per litre of soln.	Conc. of ammonia.	Nitrite-N formed per litre of soln.
$1 \times 10^{-1}N$	2.62 mg.	$2.5 \times 10^{-2}N$	1.36 mg.
1×10^{-1}	2.43	1.25×10^{-3}	1.02
5×10^{-2}	2.33	6.25×10^{-4}	0.76
2.5×10^{-2}	2.22	3.125×10^{-4}	0.64
1×10^{-2}	1.92	1.5625×10^{-4}	0.56
5×10^{-3}	1.61		

From the above results it appears that the photosensitised oxidation of ammonia is a reaction of zero order because the reaction rate is very nearly independent of concentration, *e.g.*, the initial concentration of ammonia can be varied from 0.2 to 0.025N (a change of 800%) with a resulting change of only 16% in the rate of reaction, instead of 800% change demanded by a unimolecular reaction.

Influence of the Time of Exposure.

TABLE II.

40 ml. of *M/5*-ammonia solution + 0.2 g. of ignited titania exposed to light of a 500-watt lamp.

Time.	Nitrite-nitrogen formed per liter of solution.			
	0.2N-NH ₃ .	0.1N-NH ₃ .	0.025N-NH ₃ .	0.0125N-NH ₃ .
5 hrs.	1.30 mg	1.25	1.18	1.02
10	2.59	2.48	2.36	2.01
15	3.93	3.50	3.43	3.04
20	5.30	4.70	4.49	4.12

It can be seen from the above table that the amount of nitrite formed increases proportionately with time and this is in agreement with the idea that the reaction is zero-molecular.

Effect of varying the Amount of the Photosensitiser.

TABLE III.

40 ml. of *M/5*- ammonia + titania, exposed to light from a 500-watt lamp for 5 hours.

Titania (g).	0.0031	0.0062	0.0125	0.0250	0.0500	0.1000	0.2000	0.4000	0.8000
Nitrite-N per litre of soln. (mg.)	0.05	0.13	0.27	0.49	0.56	0.94	1.30	1.32	1.35

From the above results it is evident that the rate of reaction increases at first proportionately to the increase in the amount of titania and then tends to reach a maximum value with further increase in the amount of titania. It is likely that the photosensitiser titania takes a definite *chemical* part in the reaction. Gopalarao (*loc. cit.*) postulated that the primary reaction is that between the photosensitiser and the ammonia. A molecule of titania gets activated by the absorption of a quantum of light.

The activated titania then oxidises ammonia to nitrite according to the equation,

The titanous oxide then undergoes oxidation to titanium dioxide by molecular oxygen

In order to obtain further support for this theory we kept in a bulb a solution of ammonium carbonate and titanium dioxide. The bulb was sealed after evacuation and then exposed to sunlight. Several such bulbs were exposed. After exposure the bulbs were opened and the solution in each tested for nitrite. Nitrite formation was always noticed. This production of nitrite from ammonia in the absence of oxygen clearly shows that the mechanism of the reaction is of the type postulated above.

Influence of p_{H} on the Reaction Rate.

When a solution of ammonium chloride or ammonium sulphate was exposed to light with titanium dioxide, no nitrite formation was observed. If, however, some calcium or magnesium carbonate was present, nitrite formation readily occurred. Solutions of ammonia or even ammonium carbonate also show nitrite formation when exposed to light in the presence of titania. It appears from this that it is the ammonia and not the ammonium ion that is concerned in the oxidation. It would, therefore, be interesting to study the effect of varying hydrogen ion concentrations on the rate of the reaction. In the following experiments 5 ml. of 1.6N ammonium chloride was added to 35 ml. of a suitable buffer solution of known p_{H} value. It was then exposed to light from a 500-watt lamp, after the addition of 0.2 g. of titanium dioxide. The results obtained are summarised in the following table :

TABLE IV.

p_{H} .	Nitrite-N per litre of soln.	p_{H} .	Nitrite-N per litre of soln.
7.58	0.44 mg.	9.08	0.92 mg.
8.09	0.48	9.60	0.94
8.61	0.72		

The results show that with increasing p_{H} the rate of nitrite formation increases, though it tends to reach a limiting value.

Influence of various Electrolytes on the Reaction.

It has been suggested by Gopalarao (*loc. cit.*) that the photosensitised oxidation of ammonia is a heterogeneous photocatalytic reaction occurring on the surface of the particles of the photosensitiser. Any factor tending

to reduce the effective surface of the photosensitiser must bring about a decrease in the rate of the reaction. Any substance which can displace the ammonia from the surface of the titania should also have a similar effect. When titania is shaken with ammonia solution it forms a stable suspension which contains particles that carry negative charge. On addition of electrolytes the suspension is coagulated. In this process of coagulation there is agglomeration of the smaller colloid particles into bigger ones, thus reducing the effective surface. Moreover, if polyvalent cations are added they would also displace the adsorbed ammonia. Hence it would be interesting to study the influence of different electrolytes on the rate of the photosensitised oxidation of ammonia.

TABLE V.

20 ml. of $M/2.5$ ammonia + 0.2 g. of titania + electrolyte solution + water to make up to 40 ml., exposed for 3 hours to light from a 1000-watt tungsten filament lamp.

Electrolyte used.	Electrolyte conc.	Nitrite-N per litre of the soln.
Nil	—	1.63 mg.
NaCl	0.01 N	1.40
	0.10	0.92
	0.20	0.95
BaCl ₂	0.005	1.58
	0.010	0.69
	0.100	0.71
AlCl ₃	0.010	0.40

It will be seen from the above results that addition of an electrolyte decreases the amount of nitrite formed. The degree of inhibition produced by a univalent ion like that of Na⁺ is less than that produced by the divalent Ba⁺⁺ ion. It will also be seen from the above table that increasing the concentration of the electrolyte progressively diminishes the rate of oxidation until a steady limiting rate is reached. It is very interesting to note that the limiting reaction rate with divalent ions is somewhat lower than that with univalent ions, while that with trivalent ions is still lower.

From these results we can conclude that the oxidation of ammonia occurs at the surface of titania.

It is well known that hydrated titanous acid tenaciously adsorbs ammonia. According to Weiss and Landicker (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1909, 64, 67) it is very difficult to wash away the last traces of ammonia from precipitated orthotitanous acid. Rose (*Annalen*, 1845, 53, 267) and Demoly (*Compt. rend. trav. chim.*, 1849, 8, 325) found that it is very

difficult to free precipitated metatitanic acid from the last traces of ammonia. In order to find out if ignited titanium dioxide used as photosensitiser in our experiments exhibits marked adsorption of ammonia, we have carried out experiments as follows. Merck's pure titanium dioxide was strongly ignited (to 800°), powdered and sieved first through a 60 mesh sieve and finally through a 80 mesh sieve. Ten gram portions of this oxide were shaken up with 200 ml. of a solution of ammonium hydroxide of different concentrations in Jena glass bottles and kept overnight. The supernatant liquid was very turbid and passed freely through a filter paper due to the formation of a colloid. Hence a pinch of pure potassium chloride was added to the solution in each bottle and allowed to settle. The peptised colloidal titania was thus coagulated, leaving the supernatant liquid clear. An aliquot portion of this liquid was taken out with a pipette and titrated with standard sulphuric acid to determine the amount of ammonium hydroxide remaining behind. The difference between this and the amount originally taken gives the amount of ammonia adsorbed. The results are given in the following table.

TABLE VI.

Equib. conc. (m. moles/litre)	0.48	1.26	3.22	7.33	20.0	40.8
Amount adsorbed per g. of						
TiO ₂ (m. moles × 10 ³)	6.10	9.23	10.49	13.79	17.90	22.42

From the above results it is clear that considerable adsorption of ammonia occurs at the surface of ignited titania. From Fig. 1, it will be seen that there is a tendency for the surface to be saturated with ammonia even at such a low concentration as 0.04 *M*.

That adsorption of ammonia on the titania is one of the factors controlling the photosensitised oxidation of ammonia is shown by the similarity of the curves in Figs. 1 and 2. Fig. 1 shows the variation of the adsorbed amount with concentration, while Fig. 2 represents the change of reaction rate with the concentration of ammonia.

Photosensitised Oxidation of Ammonia with Titania in Monochromatic Light of different Wave-lengths.

Aqueous solutions of ammonia are oxidised to nitrite when exposed to ultraviolet light of a quartz mercury vapour lamp but not in visible light. Gopal Rao (*loc. cit.*) has shown that there is a slow oxidation of ammonia in the light of wave-length 3000Å. According to Landsberg and Predwoditeff (*Z. Physik*, 1925, 31, 544) the adsorption spectrum of ammonia consists mainly of the bands 1858Å, 1935Å, 1990Å, 2025Å, 2062Å, 2144Å, and also 2195Å. But in the presence of titanium dioxide the oxidation of ammonia occurs even in the visible region. Results given in the following table show that the oxidation takes place quite rapidly in light of 4050Å and that there is a slow oxidation even in the light of longer wave-lengths.

TABLE VII.

40 C.c. of ammonia + 0.2 g. of TiO₂ exposed for 20 hours to light from a 1000-watt tungsten filament lamp, through light filters.

Filter.	Transmitted radiation.	Nitrite nitrogen formed per litre in 20 hours.
Yellow : Wallace, M and S, No. 5 and No. 7	5300-5850Å	Traces.
Green, Do. No. 7 and No. 8	5000-5550Å	0.12 mg.
Blue, Do. No. 8 and No. 3	4450-5000Å	0.15
Violet : 0.02N-Iodine in carbon tetrachloride (3 cm. layer) + 0.05% quinine hydrochloride, 1 cm. layer.	4050Å	4.24

The quinine hydrochloride solution in the last filter undergoes decomposition in the light and is therefore discarded at the end of every hour and replaced by fresh solution. Similar results have been reported by Gopal Rao (*loc. cit.*) working with quartz mercury vapour lamp and filters. Hallet (*Proc. Amer. Soc. Testing Materials*, 1923, 399; *Chem. Met. Eng.*, 1923, 64, 29) has shown that titanium dioxide strongly absorbs in the near ultraviolet and ultraviolet parts of the spectrum. Thus titanium dioxide absorbs strongly those wave-lengths which ammonia by itself cannot absorb. Recently Goodeve and Kitchener (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, 34, 570) have stated from study of the reflection spectrum of titania powder that the threshold of absorption lies at about 3800Å although the position varies slightly according to the method of preparation and treatment of the sample.

DISCUSSION.

The main features of the photosensitised oxidation of ammonia as revealed in this study are:

1. The oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in the presence of titania and sunlight occurs even if air be excluded.

2. Increase in the amount of titania produces an increase in the reaction rate but this soon reaches a limiting value with a constant intensity of light.

3. The amount of nitrite formed increases proportionately with the time of exposure.

4. With constant amount of titania the reaction velocity does not increase in proportion with the increase in concentration of ammonia; only a very slight increase in the reaction rate is produced by a very large increase in the concentration of ammonia.

5. The reaction is retarded by traces of salts of colourless cations like, Na^+ , Ba^{++} , Al^{+++} . The divalent barium ions are more effective retarders than the monovalent sodium ions and the trivalent aluminium ions are more effective than the divalent barium ions.

6. In the presence of titanium dioxide the oxidation of ammonia occurs even in visible light of wave-length $4050\text{\AA}$ and even of higher wave-lengths.

(1) and (2) indicate that the photosensitiser takes part in the reaction. (3) and (4) indicate that the reaction is zero-molecular. This, taken along with (5) shows that adsorption plays an important part in this reaction. The reaction appears to be a heterogeneous catalytic reaction taking place at the surface of titania. A heterogeneous photocatalytic reaction of this kind is somewhat complex and presents a variety of interesting aspects from the theoretical standpoint. When a chemical reaction occurs in a heterogeneous system, there are superimposed upon the specific chemical effects certain interfacial factors, which operate at the boundary of the phases. Dissolved molecules may react with the solid, or undergo catalytic transformation at its surface. The solid may be present as a sediment, or dispersed as a suspension or a colloid. Dissolved molecules must strike and be adsorbed on the surface of the solid before reaction can occur. It has to be realised that the seat of the reaction is the adsorbed layer. And that except in so far as it acts as the reservoir which regulates the concentration of the molecules in this layer, the solution phase is practically outside this reaction. It is the active mass of the substance in the adsorbed layer that determines the rate and order of the reaction. From the Langmuir adsorption isotherm, it is known that the amount of substance adsorbed is

nearly independent of concentration, when adsorption is strong. So also the rate of reaction will be practically constant and independent of concentration. The reaction becomes one of zero order. This has been found to be the case with the photosensitised oxidation of ammonia in the presence of titanium dioxide.

In the case of a heterogeneous photocatalytic reaction there is a further complication. We have to take into account the intensity of the light and the concentration of the light absorbing constituent, *viz.*, the photosensitiser, titania in this case. In Table III it is seen that with increasing amounts of titania, the rate of reaction increases at first proportionately and finally tends to attain a limiting value. This is probably because with the higher amounts of titania the light intensity is becoming the limiting factor. With the smaller amounts of titania, the light intensity from a 500-watt lamp can be assumed to be fairly high; so the amount of light absorbing constituent, titania, determines the rate of the reaction. Hence the rate of reaction increases gradually as the amount of titania increases. But a stage will arrive, when the concentration of titania is no longer limiting the reaction and the intensity of light limits the speed of the reaction. Thus if the intensity of light is kept constant a further increase in the amount of titania does not increase the speed of the reaction. If this hypothesis be correct, an increase in the light intensity at this stage should produce an increase in the reaction rate. In order to put this hypothesis to experimental test, different quantities of titania with the same concentration of ammonia are exposed for 5 hours to light issuing from a 500-watt lamp and also from a 1000-watt lamp. The results are given in the following table.

TABLE VIII.

40 Ml. of *M*/5-ammonia solution exposed with titania for 5 hours.

Titania taken.	Nitrite-N formed per litre	
	with a 500-watt lamp.	with a 1000-watt lamp.
0·8000 g.	1·35 mg.	3·78 mg.
0·4000	1·32	3·41
0·2000	1·30	2·71
0·1000	0·94	—
0·0500	0·56	—
0·0250	0·49	—
0·0125	0·27	—

From the above results it is clear that with a 500-watt lamp the reaction rate reaches a limiting value at about 0.2 g. of titania. With a 1000-watt lamp, the amount of nitrite obtained with 0.2 g. of titania is doubled and increases with increasing amounts of titania.

These results are somewhat similar to those of Blackman and Smith (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1911, 83B, 389) on photosynthesis. It was Blackman who first broke away from the conception of a single optimum factor and developed the theory of interaction of various factors. Blackman and Smith studied the effect of varying concentrations of carbon dioxide on the photosynthetic activity of aquatic plants, *Fontinalis antipyretica* and *Elodea*. They state, "in the weaker solutions of carbon dioxide the curve shows steadily increasing assimilation proportional to the increase of carbon dioxide supply. Here the light intensity and temperature are in excess. But at a certain point, sharply defined increase of carbon dioxide concentration is no longer followed by further increase of assimilation but the value of the assimilation remains at a fixed level.... This part of the curve is due to the limiting action of either illumination or the temperature.... Had a more intense light and a higher temperature been fixed upon, then the ascending part of the curve would have been prolonged further, and a fixed (but higher) level only attained with a greater concentration of carbon dioxide. With less light the limiting value would have been arrived at sooner." In a similar way, Warburg (*Biochem. Z.*, 1919, 100, 230) working on the photosynthetic activity of unicellular green algae, *Chlorella*, found that at low concentrations of carbon dioxide, the rate of photosynthesis is closely proportional to the carbon dioxide concentration. Above a concentration about 2×10^{-6} moles per liter, progressive increase in the carbon dioxide concentration results in a continuously smaller increase in the rate of photosynthesis until finally the latter becomes independent of CO_2 concentration. Warburg interprets these results on the basis that the rate of photosynthesis is proportional to the concentration of carbon dioxide, and to the concentration of a second substance which reacts with carbon dioxide. Harder (*Jahrb. Wiss. Bot.*, 1921, 60, 531) from an extensive study, stated that certain modifications are necessary, in the simple principle of limiting factors, proposed by Blackman and Smith (*loc. cit.*).

From what has been said above, it appears that the photosynthetic reaction in the green plant is a heterogeneous photosensitized reaction, where possibly the photosensitizer (like the titania in our reaction) takes an active part in the cycle of chemical reactions, though finally regenerated at the end of the cycle.

It has been definitely established by our experiments that the photosen-

sitiser, titanium dioxide, takes an active role in the photosensitised oxidation of ammonia. It is likely that a Ti^{++++} ion in a molecule of TiO_2 on the surface gets electronically excited on the absorption of quantum of light. An electron is raised to a higher energy level and according to Franck and Haber (*Sitzber. Preuss. Akad. Wiss.* 1931, 250) such a molecule, atom or ion which possesses an unoccupied electronic level can take up an electron from a reducing substance which functions as an electron donor.

Thus

The photoactive particle takes up an electron and hence gets reduced. The reducing substance which donates the electron gets oxidised.

This mechanism of photosensitisation by titania receives support from the observation of Goodeve and Kitchener (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, 34, 902) that the threshold of absorption for solid titania lies in the same region of the spectrum as that of the ions in solution. This may be taken to indicate that the absorption of light by this substance is due to the titanium ions and these are raised to an excited level.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
ANDHRA UNIVERSITY,
WALTAIR.

Received November 11, 1940.

The experimental work reported here formed part of a thesis presented by K.S.M. for the M.Sc. (Hons.) degree of the Andhra University in 1936.